

Project Number:
101095314

Project Acronym:
aUPaEU

Project title:
A University Partnership for Acceleration of European Universities

Report on the implementation gap analysis and the ideation of the digital transition

Version 0.3 – 09 May 2024

Deliverable 5.1

Deliverable

<i>Project Title</i>	A University Partnership for Acceleration of European Universities
<i>Project Acronym</i>	aUPaEU
<i>Grant Agreement Number</i>	101095314
<i>Topic Id</i>	HORIZON-WIDERA-2022-ERA-01-51 - Acceleration Services in support of the institutional transformation of Higher Education Institutions
<i>Programme:</i>	Horizon Europe Framework Programme (HORIZON)
<i>Call:</i>	European Research Area (HORIZON-WIDERA-2022-ERA-01)
<i>Type of action:</i>	HORIZON-CSA HORIZON Coordination and Support Actions
<i>Type of MGA:</i>	HORIZON Action Grant Budget-Based [HORIZON-AG]
<i>Project starting date</i>	1 Jan 2023
<i>Duration</i>	60 months
<i>Partners</i>	Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya - UPC Karlsruher Institut für Technologie - KIT Institut Polytechnique de Grenoble- INP GRENOBLE Politecnico di Torino - POLITO Uniwersytet im. Adama Mickiewicza w Poznaniu - AMU
<i>Work Package</i>	WP5 – Implementation of Digital Transition

<i>Deliverable Related No</i>	D5.1
<i>Deliverable No</i>	D12
<i>Deliverable name</i>	Report on the implementation gap analysis and the ideation of the digital transition
<i>Lead Beneficiary</i>	Universitat Politecnica de Catalunya (UPC)
<i>Deliverable type</i>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> R - Document, report <input type="checkbox"/> DEM - Demonstrator, pilot, prototype <input type="checkbox"/> DMP – Data Management Plan
<i>Dissemination level</i>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Public — fully open <input type="checkbox"/> Sensitive — limited under the conditions of the Grant Agreement <input type="checkbox"/> EU classified—RESTREINT-UE/EU-RESTRICTED, CONFIDENTIEL-UE/EU-CONFIDENTIAL, SECRET-UE/EU-SECRET under Decision 2015/444
<i>Deliverable due date</i>	31 Dec 2023
<i>New due date</i>	10 May 2024
<i>Approval date</i>	30 May 2024
<i>Status</i>	Approved
<i>Author(s) – Partner(s)</i>	Jesus Alcober, UPC Juan López, UPC Alba Roma, UPC

<i>Document version and delivery date</i>	v0.3 – 09 May 2024
<i>File identifier</i>	w aUPaEU_WP5_D5.1_implementation gap_v0.3 .docx
<i>Keywords</i>	Agora, gap analysis, Implementation
<i>Abstract</i>	This document provides an overview of the Agora platform, a comprehensive solution for accelerating digital transformation initiatives within Higher Education Institutions (HEIs). It delves into the technical foundation of Agora, the implementation of various acceleration services, and the technical implementation of the platform, highlighting the key results achieved in terms of user adoption and impact on HEI digital transformation efforts.

History of changes

<i>Version</i>	<i>Date</i>	<i>Author(s) Partner(s)</i>	<i>Reviewer(s) Partner(s)</i>	<i>Description</i>
v0.1	15 Dec 2023	Jesus Alcober - UPC Juan López - UPC Alba Roma - UPC		Initial version
v0.1	22 Dec 2023		Michael Anger - KIT Jacek Marciniak -AMU	Overall review and remarks

v0.2	28 Dec 2023	Jesus Alcober - UPC Juan López - UPC Alba Roma - UPC		consolidation of the received feedback and review
v0.3	09 May 2024	Jesus Alcober - UPC Juan López - UPC Alba Roma - UPC		consolidation of the received feedback and review

Document Updates

This revised version of the deliverable incorporates the feedback from the European Commission, addressing the following inquiries:

The document provides a description about the technical foundation of the Agora platform identifying Odoo business management software as its baseline. It then explores the implementation of various acceleration services within the Agora portal and the related technical solutions adopted.

The document is by nature a technical one and provides some useful elements for externals in case the adopted technological solutions and approaches could be interesting for possible replication in other contexts.

However, the report does not sufficiently link its contents to the previous project outcomes, justifying for example the list of the implemented acceleration services as an outcome of previous project activities and linking them to the relevant deliverables allowing the reader to follow the project path appropriately. A revision of the document to make this link more evident and provide a consequential nature to the outcomes described in this deliverable is necessary

The document now explicitly addresses these comments:

In order to provide more context regarding the technical results associated with previous project outcomes, two additional sections have been added, the 1.1 Acceleration Services Requirements and the 5.1 Technical meetings with service users. The section 1.1 serves as a linkage to the project outcomes outlined in D2.1 and D4.1. This section justifies the

compilation of implemented acceleration services as a direct outcome of previous project activities. The section 5.1 outlines the co-creation with stakeholders through technical meetings.

Abbreviation list

AI	Artificial Intelligence
aUPaEU	A University Partnership for Acceleration of European Universities
CRM	Customer Relationship Management
D2.1	aUPaEU deliverable number D5 from WP2, Preliminary analysis and plan, outline of the acceleration services catalogue
D6.1	aUPaEU deliverable number D15 from WP6, Draft report about the planned test with user groups
D7.1	aUPaEU deliverable number D18 from WP7, First reporting on Communication and Dissemination plans and stakeholders mapping
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
ERP	Enterprise Resource Planning
HEI	Higher Education Institutions
GA	Grant Agreement
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
LLM	Large Language Model
OA	Open Access
WP	Work Package

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1 Introduction

In the ever-evolving landscape of higher education, the pursuit of digital transformation has become an imperative for Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) seeking to remain competitive and impactful. Recognizing this critical need, the University Partnership for Acceleration of European Universities (aUPaEU) project has emerged as a beacon of innovation, introducing a comprehensive approach to accelerating HEI transformation through the unifying power of information and the strategic deployment of value-added services.

At the heart of the aUPaEU initiative lies the Agora platform, a centralised hub designed to seamlessly integrate and streamline information from disparate sources, including European platforms, HEI systems, and Agora data. This unified information ecosystem serves as a transformative foundation for unlocking the true potential of acceleration services.

The Agora system infrastructure comprises four key components, each playing a crucial role in harmonising information flows and driving transformative change.

- **European Platform Integration:** Agora establishes seamless connections to European datasets and open data platforms, such as EOSC¹, OpenAIRE², and EURAXESS³, among others, through APIs, ensuring real-time access to a wealth of relevant information. This integration streamlines data access and ensures that HEIs have access to the most up-to-date information, empowering informed decision-making.
- **Acceleration Service Layer:** Agora provides a value-added service layer that sits atop the integrated information, offering data analysis, trend identification, and stakeholder matching capabilities. This layer enhances the value proposition of Agora by providing actionable insights that inform the delivery of tailored acceleration services.
- **Resource and Personnel Management:** Agora effectively manages information about resources and personnel involved in acceleration services, ensuring efficient utilisation and accessibility. This management system streamlines service delivery and facilitates collaboration among stakeholders, fostering a culture of collective expertise.
- **Stakeholder Profiling and Identification:** Agora facilitates the exchange, analysis, and profiling of stakeholder information, enabling the identification of suitable partners for digital transformation support. This identification process ensures that HEIs connect

¹ [EOSC Portal](#), (European Open Science Cloud): A federated open science infrastructure that provides researchers with access to a wide range of scientific research data and resources; last accessed 07 December 2023

² [OpenAIRE](#), (Open Access Infrastructure for Research in Europe): A repository for research publications and datasets that facilitates the discovery, access, and usage of open research materials across Europe; last accessed 07 December 2023

³ [EURAXESS](#), (European Research Area and Mobility Programme): A network of information, advice, and support services for researchers in Europe, helping them to find funding, jobs, and collaboration opportunities across the continent; last accessed 07 December 2023

with the most relevant experts, unlocking a network of knowledge and expertise that accelerates their transformation journey.

The Agora platform emerges as a transformative catalyst for HEIs, empowering them to navigate the complexities of digital transformation with greater agility and achieve their strategic goals. By leveraging Agora, HEIs can:

- **Gain comprehensive insights into their own resources and expertise:** Agora provides a centralised repository of information about HEIs, including their research facilities, expertise, and human resources. This comprehensive overview empowers HEIs to better understand their strengths and areas for improvement, guiding their transformation efforts effectively.
- **Identify and connect with suitable partners:** Agora's intelligent matching algorithm identifies and connects HEIs with the most appropriate partners for their specific areas of transformation. This strategic alignment ensures that HEIs receive the most relevant support from experts with the right skills and experience.
- **Receive personalised recommendations for acceleration services:** Agora analyses HEIs' needs and stakeholder profiles to provide personalised recommendations for acceleration services. This tailored approach ensures that HEIs receive the most impactful support, aligning their transformation efforts with their unique goals and objectives.

The aUPaEU project, with its Agora platform at its core, represents a paradigm shift in supporting HEI transformation. By addressing the fragmented nature of information systems, providing value-added acceleration services, and facilitating stakeholder identification, Agora sets a new standard for empowering HEIs across Europe to achieve their digital transformation aspirations.

As HEIs embark on their digital transformation journeys, aUPaEU and the Agora platform stand as unwavering allies, providing the tools, resources, and expertise necessary to navigate this exciting yet challenging landscape. With aUPaEU's unwavering commitment to innovation and collaboration, HEIs can confidently embrace digital transformation, propelling them towards a future of enhanced learning, research, and impact.

The establishment of the Agora necessitates the selection of a technical platform that effectively addresses the identified challenges, particularly the complex business processes involved in offering and consuming the acceleration service catalogue. As previously mentioned, we will initiate this endeavour by developing a specialised library of acceleration services tailored to the realm of research and innovation. It's crucial to recognize that the business process terminology utilised in this context extends beyond mere monetization; it encompasses the operational procedures of a multifaceted organisation where diverse functional groups interact.

In view of these considerations, the most suitable platform type aligns with the ERP (enterprise resource planning) category⁴. This software, renowned for its well-structured processes dating back to the last century, provides a robust foundation for managing Agora's intricate operations. A comprehensive survey of ERP solutions, conducted by Ganesh (2016), unveils Openbravo⁵ and Odoo⁶ as the open-source frontrunners in this domain. This aligns with our aUPaEU project's unwavering commitment to embracing open-source software.

Consonant with our preference for open-source solutions, a comparative analysis by Gómez-Llanez (2020) between Openbravo and Odoo concludes that Odoo emerges as the optimal implementation option. This finding aligns with our extensive experience of over a decade working with Odoo in its open-source community edition⁷. We believe that Odoo's mature and comprehensive features, coupled with its open-source nature, make it the ideal platform to underpin Agora's operations.

Proceeding from the introduction, the document delves into the technical foundation of the Agora platform, unveiling the Odoo business management software as its underlying structure. It then explores the implementation of various acceleration services within the Agora, including the Agora portal, email marketing tools, a research infrastructure catalogue, a research and innovation proposals platform, job opportunities and internships, consulting, training, and mentoring services, feedback mechanisms, events, conferences, workshops, and showcases. Authentication methods such as eduGAIN and LinkedIn integration are also addressed. The technical implementation of the Agora platform is then examined, highlighting the generic module for standardised element creation and management, along with the incorporation of an artificial intelligence assistant to enhance user experience and provide personalised recommendations. The section concludes with a summary of the key results achieved, including user numbers, service requests handled, and the overall impact on accelerating digital transformation initiatives within HEIs. A comprehensive list of references concludes the document.

1.1 Acceleration Services Requirements

The WP5 of aUPaEU project has the task of implementing the digital transition, designing and developing platforms which provide solutions for the implementation of acceleration services.

Based on Section 5 of D2.1 titled "Dynamic Methodology for Acceleration Services Development: A Comprehensive Plan," this strategy comprises seven key phases. These include (1) engaging stakeholders, (2) analysing requirements, (3) inspecting data, (4) defining business processes, (5) implementation, (6) conducting tests, and (7) disseminating

⁴ [List of ERP software packages - Wikipedia](#), last accessed 07 December 2023

⁵ [Openbravo](#), last accessed 07 December 2023

⁶ [Odoo](#), last accessed 07 December 2023

⁷ [Community | Odoo](#), last accessed 07 December 2023

outcomes. Each phase plays a crucial role in the continuous improvement and enhancement of acceleration services, with the ultimate goal of addressing stakeholder requirements and fostering innovation within the higher education domain.

The methodology of work in order to better identify the implementation gap of the designed tools has been based on co-creation in **step 2**, since the beginning of the project. Co-creation is the practice of collaborating with different stakeholders to guide the design process, and the result of this collaboration is the list of the implemented acceleration services. This offers more value to the new developments, as participants with different roles come together and provide a range of perspectives.

In the context of the aUPaEU project, co-creation has been clearly delineated, particularly between WP2, as evidenced by D2.1, which provides input for the business process description in WP4 through D4.1, specifically for **step 4**. Additionally, it pertains to **step 3** for data analysis in WP3 and is anticipated to continue in the future with WP6 for **step 6**. With respect to WP2, they have dealt with the analysis and methodology towards R&I acceleration services, identifying the general user's requirements. This resulted in a list of acceleration services defined in D2.1, which we based our work guidelines on. Regarding WP6, future collaboration has been foreseen, as they will deal with the testing and validation of the acceleration services in **step 6**, more specifically, the testing on the platforms developed by WP5, with the users which have been part of the created services (See D6.1). During these first months, information about users of the platform has been collected for their future testing.

On this deliverable, a definition of the chosen platform will be elaborated, as well as each of the services developed is going to be described from the technical point of view. On the section 5 of this document where the results of the technical implementation are presented, a comparative table comprising the developed services associated with the defined on the Table 1.1 from the point of view of the users which demanded those services.

Table 1.1. List of Acceleration Services defined on D2.1

Acceleration Services Requirements

N°	Acceleration Service
1	Supply of Agoras tailored to HEIs' or Alliances' needs
2	Catalogue of research infrastructures and TTOs
3	Events, Conferences, and Workshops
4	Accessing Grants and Funding
5	Coaching and Support Mechanism for HEIs
6	Methodology for an Investment Strategy
7	Stakeholders management

N°	Acceleration Service
8	Showcases

2 Odoo - a business management software tool

Odoo is an open-source business management software encompassing tools such as Customer Relationship Management (CRM), Enterprise Resource Planning (ERP), and project management (Moss, 2019). This document illustrates the utilisation of a business management tool as a network management solution for inter-university collaborations.

Customer Relationship Management (CRM) serves as a strategy for managing interactions with customers and potential customers. It aids in organising and streamlining processes, building relationships, improving customer service, and enhancing profitability. The university management tool required by the aUPaEU project differs from typical corporate needs, focusing not on financial aspects but on connecting contact points that share similar interests in research, creating potential collaborations, and disseminating educational content within the university community. Contact management is therefore a critical aspect to this necessity, prompting the consideration of CRM as a viable architecture for the provided service.

The core strength of Odoo lies in its modular and extensible architecture. Exploiting this, we customised its functionalities by modifying core applications and introducing new modules. This initial section of the document aims to highlight the pre-existing Odoo modules that addressed the majority of architectural needs, while also acknowledging its limitations and identified gaps.

2.1 Multi Company

Multicompany functionality in Odoo is a feature that enables management of multiple entities or subsidiaries under the same platform. It facilitates the maintenance of separate CRM processes and projects for each entity while benefiting from a shared infrastructure, granting a high level of autonomy to each company. Access rights are important to define the functionalities permitted for each user and the information visible to them. This is particularly important for safeguarding sensitive data, ensuring that information pertaining to one company remains only accessible to that specific entity.

In the case of aUPaEU, the specific use case involves defining a company for each university alliance in collaboration, that is a company in Odoo corresponds to an Agora. This includes the aUPaEU Agora, which is an internal company dedicated to the aUPaEU project and other companies designed to engage with potential stakeholders of the project.

2.2 Contacts Module

In order to build a network between researchers around the world, a database must be created, holding relevant information about each researcher, their areas of expertise, and their ongoing projects. The Contacts module within Odoo proves to be a pivotal component in fulfilling this requirement.

This module allows organising and managing the contact information systematically. Separating “individuals” from “companies” (institutions in this case) allows creating hierarchy relationships. Thanks to the “Partner multi relation” add-on, higher level relations can also be added in order to define specific roles in big projects within an alliance of universities.

Figure 2.1. Contact cards and relations offered by Odoo Contacts module

2.3 Project Module

The Project module is mostly used for the internal aUPaEU project management, using Kanban - a lean project management tool. Kanban visually organises projects into stages for streamlined workflow. Within each task, Odoo features a messages thread, facilitating email exchanges among task followers/participants. This ensures transparent communication and efficient tracking of feature development progress. Additionally, the module incorporates timesheets to record hours invested in projects, offering valuable metrics for resource allocation and project timelines. This data allows for retrospective analysis, contributing to continuous improvements in project planning and management.

2.4 Website Module

While Odoo primarily serves as a management back-office tool, it incorporates a website module that simplifies website/user interface (UI) configuration without requiring extensive knowledge of web development. It uses configurable snippet blocks, not only for the general headers, text, or images, but also for displaying information from the back-office tool, including inventories and products.

While this feature is powerful, it has its limitations. In the following sections, we will get into the methods employed to improve this module further, thereby introducing functionalities not initially available in the provided blocks.

Figure 2.2. Some of the provided snippet blocks offered by Odoo Website module

Multiple websites can be created, each of them pointing to a different domain. This centralised platform allows the configuration of multiple services from one common source of information and management tool. External user interaction is primarily facilitated through the form block, enabling the creation of contact forms, each associated with a specific sales team. Furthermore, new opportunities can be generated from leads generated by interested users.

2.5 CRM

It has been mentioned that the CRM is an important tool for managing interactions between users, acting as the mediator between contact points. Similar to the projects' module, it also maintains a record of the email thread associated with a specific opportunity. Additionally, the CRM provides a centralised hub for storing and accessing relevant documents and notes related to the ongoing interactions, contributing to a more organised management of customer relationships.

Figure 2.3. Creation of CRM opportunities from user interface

3 Acceleration Services Implementations

The principal objective of this technological platform is to offer acceleration services to Higher Education Institutions. Applied in this context, acceleration services for Higher Education Institutions are programs, services, infrastructures, or initiatives designed to help and support HEIs in implementing strategies and pathways for institutional transformation. More specifically, as stated in WP4 Acceleration Services Catalog, these services largely apply to one of the following goals:

- Facilitate resource and infrastructure services.
- Promote research professions and careers.
- Improve R&I collaboration between academia and industry.
- Boost open science.
- Involve citizens and support societal issues.

In the following section, we aim to explore some of the acceleration services defined within the aUPaEU project, detailing their implementation within the platform and services they offer.

3.1 Agora

Agora denotes the virtual space allocated to each university alliance. It is a digital hub designed for collaboration, connection and also serves as a repository for uploading and sharing resources of interest among alliance members. Each alliance has been set up as a company, and their Agoras have been configured using the website module. That means that a company in Odoo corresponds to an Agora. Currently, two Agoras have been developed—one for the Unite! Alliance and another for the EPICUR alliance, being them our core stakeholders as defined in deliverable D7.1.

Figure 3.1. Unite! Agora and EPICUR Agora

3.2 Email Marketing

To enhance communication and collaboration across diverse projects within the Odoo platform, it became essential to establish dedicated communication channels. Currently, two key functionalities provide such services.

3.2.1 Newsletter

The Odoo Email Marketing module allows the creation of Mailing Lists. Multiple lists can be created, a general one for each Agora, and other for more specific purposes, an example would be the “Reading Club” mailing list, which shares the latest news about the undergoing readings and specify the details of their monthly meeting. This channel is dedicated to unidirectional communication and it is very powerful to disseminate general communications to interested readers. Users can subscribe via the website.

3.2.2 Mail Groups

For a collaborative and bidirectional exchange of messages and communications among team members, Odoo incorporates an add-on that facilitates the management of mailing lists through the creation of mailing groups. Team members can easily subscribe to these groups, email the specified group address using an email alias, and exchange responses within a group thread. Additionally, the exchanged emails within these groups can be viewed on the website, creating a forum-like space for communication.

3.3 Catalogue of Research Infrastructures

One of the key acceleration services focuses on research infrastructures, helping users in locating research laboratories or facilities based on specific scientific fields or available equipment. This service has been implemented for both alliances, Unite! and EPICUR. Being the first service developed in both platforms, proves this to be a core Agora feature.

The listed infrastructures can be expanded to see a short description of their facilities and are linked to a specific infrastructure page with all information related to the equipment, scientific domains, keywords, home partner institutions, and more. For each infrastructure, there is a contact button which directs the interested user to a contact form, from which it can address any questions related. When submitted, this form automatically generates a lead in the CRM, assigning it to the dedicated sales team responsible for managing the infrastructures. The CRM integration is particularly significant as it automates the process from initial contact to lead generation, ensuring no potential interest is lost.

Figure 3.2. EPICUR and Unite! Research Infrastructures

Given that Odoo does not provide a module specific to store a database of infrastructures and displaying them on the website, some development work was necessary. Additionally, different customised fields were needed for each alliance to define a research infrastructure. Once the fields were established, an Odoo model was created for each alliance, together with the configuration of corresponding back-office views. These views are designed for allowing administrators to manage the infrastructures effectively without extensive technical knowledge, through simple creating, updating, or deleting operations.

The website's visualisation was achieved by creating a custom snipped block within the website module, designed to display a list of elements based on an Odoo model. This custom website block makes the process efficient, offering a standardised view for lists of elements by simply adding configuration parameters. This eliminates the need for extensive code development for each alliance website and underscores the system's scalability and

maintenance. For a technical breakdown of the custom website block and the specific configuration parameters used, refer to point 3.2.

3.4 Research and Innovation Proposals

Another acceleration service offered within the Unite! platform is the Research and Innovation Proposals feature. This service provides a collaborative environment where users can discover, contribute to, and initiate research and innovation initiatives. The implementation of this service within the Unite! alliance aims to promote collaborative research and innovation across institutions.

The platform allows users to search for proposals via the custom website block used to display research infrastructures, ensuring consistency across the platform. Proposals are listed with essential details like title, description, associated institution, contact options, and are linked to a specific page with all the details. The contact button also creates a lead in the CRM whenever a user is interested in a specific proposal.

The screenshot shows the 'Research and Innovation Proposals' section of the Unite! platform. At the top, there is a navigation bar with 'Home', 'Infrastructures', 'R&I collaboration', 'Events', and 'Contact us'. On the right, there are 'Sign in' and 'Contact Us' buttons. The main heading is 'Research and Innovation Proposals'. Below it, a sub-heading reads 'Collaborative Research and Innovation Proposals Platform. Learn how it works here!'. There are two buttons: 'CREATE A PROPOSAL' and 'GIVE US FEEDBACK ABOUT THE PLATFORM'. A search bar contains 'Search proposals...' and a 'Search' button. A 'Filter by tags...' input field is also present. Below the search bar, there is a 'Filter by home partner institution...' section with buttons for 'Grenoble INP - UGA', 'POLITO', 'UPC', and 'WROCLAW TECH'. The main content area displays a list of proposals, each with a title, a date, and a 'CONTACT' button:

- Wind turbine power curve optimization via Active Flow Control** - until 2023-12-19
- Digital Awareness for Older Adults** - until 2023-12-31
- Best Practices in IT and Business Processes** - until 2023-12-31
- Enhancing Agriculture Through Drone Technology** - until 2023-12-31
- Enhancing University Alliance Acceleration Services** - until 2023-12-31

Figure 3.2. Unite! Research and Innovation Proposals

Furthermore, the platform enhances user engagement through a tag subscription feature. Users can subscribe to specific tags related to their interests, and the system will

automatically send them an email notification whenever a new proposal matching their subscribed keywords has been validated. This keeps users informed about the latest research opportunities and encourages active participation within the alliance.

Tags: [R&I project proposal external funding](#) , [Project beneficiary](#) , [Associated partner \(e.g., for MSCA-DNs to confer title or E+s\)](#) (subscribed) , [Digital, Industry & Space](#) (subscribed) , [Climate, Energy & Mobility](#) , [Food, Bioeconomy, Neutral Resources, Agriculture & Environment](#)

Click on tags to subscribe and receive updates on related research proposals.

Figure 3.3. Research and Innovation Proposals Tags subscription

A standout feature of this service is the 'Create a Proposal' form. This form is a customised Odoo website form that seamlessly integrates with the backend, enabling users to submit their research proposals directly through the website interface. The form includes fields for the proposal title, description, URL, expiration date, type of collaboration, topic, and type of collaborator, ensuring comprehensive input for potential research opportunities. Once the proposal is validated, it appears listed on the public website.

unitel | University Alliance for Research, Innovation and Enterprise Home Infrastructures R&I collaboration ▾ Events Contact us ▾ Sign in Contact Us

Collaborative **Research and Innovation** Proposals Platform

Create a Research Proposal

Title *

Description

Url

Expiration Date

Type of collaboration

<input type="checkbox"/> R&I project proposal external funding	<input type="checkbox"/> R&I project proposal internal funding (ex. seed funding)	<input type="checkbox"/> Talent (MSCA, PhD thesis, etc.)
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Topic of the collaboration

<input type="checkbox"/> Health	<input type="checkbox"/> Culture, Creativity & Inclusive Society	<input type="checkbox"/> Civil Security for Society
<input type="checkbox"/> Digital, Industry & Space	<input type="checkbox"/> Climate, Energy & Mobility	<input type="checkbox"/> Food, Bioeconomy, Neutral Resources, Agriculture & Environment
<input type="checkbox"/> HE Widening participation	<input type="checkbox"/> Training (mobility, PhD Thesis abroad, etc.)	

Type of collaborator

<input type="checkbox"/> Project beneficiary	<input type="checkbox"/> Coordinator	<input type="checkbox"/> Third-party
<input type="checkbox"/> Associated partner (e.g., for MSCA-DNs to confer title or E+s)	<input type="checkbox"/> Host institution (e.g. for teaching mobility, administrative staff mobility, thesis abroad, etc...)	

Submit

Figure 3.4. Unite! Research and Innovation Proposals Creation Form

3.5 Feedback

This platform places significant emphasis on interaction metrics, whether it's between contact points or from users engaging with the platform's offered services. There are two feedback mechanisms which are currently in use. The first one is a simple satisfaction rating with a comments box. Alternatively, more detailed feedback using the Odoo Surveys add-on which allows configuring surveys with a set of questions, providing valuable metrics based on the corresponding responses.

Thank you for rating our services!

Figure 3.5. Feedback options

3.6 Events, Conferences and Workshops

One important acceleration service is focused on organising training sessions, including conferences and workshops. These events are usually dynamic and require a simple platform to create events and a user interface for accessing upcoming events. Interested users should be able to register to events and potentially receive email instructions related to the event.

Odoo provides an Events module that fulfils this requirement. The user interface presents a list of events, each of them providing comprehensive details such as event title, date, description, and registration status.

For organisers, the Odoo events module offers a back-office tracking system. It allows for efficient management of attendee lists and logistical details for event planning. This functionality is represented in a Kanban-style interface, which organisers can use to monitor the event lifecycle from announcement to completion.

Figure 3.6. Agora Events feature

3.7 Showcases

In this project, the concept of showcase refers to compact website displays designed specifically for the promotion of a project. These showcases are provided when a single Agora web page is insufficient to accommodate all the content and functionalities of a project. Within university alliances, teams often develop deliverables for new educational tools. While these may align with the acceleration services offered by the Agora, they may also require an independent user interface. Showcases offer an independent user interface/website within the same platform, so that all contact persons are centrally stored on the same network, and internal CRM management is also shared within the alliance.

Essentially, an Odoo company such as Unite! has multiple websites associated – the Agora (the primary one), and those related with each showcase. As it has been mentioned, the website edition offers a very intuitive platform where people can add content to it easily. The separation of features in different websites allows selective access to the website editing feature. This means that certain groups of people can focus on editing their showcase without being granted access to all other features of the Agora website.

Some examples of the showcases which are currently being set up can be seen on the following image: the “Well-being community” focusing on developing tools and actions to address the challenges of IDEA - Inclusion, Diversity, Equity & Accessibility; the “Space Tech Unite!” focusing on aerospace related projects; the “Staff hub Unite!” focusing on providing tools to all personnel of Unite! alliance; the “Online toolkit” focusing on providing joint programmes and collaborative educational offerings.

Figure 3.7. Unite! Showcases

3.8 Authentication methods

Odoo platform uses two authentication methods to provide secure and convenient access: eduGAIN for institutions and LinkedIn for professionals. eduGAIN validates email addresses and provides official information, while LinkedIn authentication links to LinkedIn profiles for additional details. Of course, the platform will make sure to process all personal information in compliance with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR).

3.8.1 eduGAIN authentication

In educational platforms where sensible data is restricted to individuals within a specific university alliance, an authentication method that validates the email of a particular institution becomes a necessity. To address this need, eduGAIN authentication has been integrated into the Odoo platform. Even if the user is not yet in the system, they can log in and create their account using their usual institution authentication method. With eduGAIN authentication, we acquire the official name and email of the user, along with their role within the institution (student, teacher staff, etc.)

3.8.2 LinkedIn authentication

LinkedIn is one of the most popular social media platforms for professional interactions. Considering its significance, we incorporated LinkedIn authentication into the platform. Through this authentication method, contacts are created with their name, email, LinkedIn profile link, current job position, and profile photo. We are initiating the process of seeking a legal expert's evaluation to analyse the GDPR implications of this authentication method, ensuring compliance with the GDPR and the distinct regulations across European countries.

4 Technical Implementation

This section of the document describes the more technical aspects of the platform's development.

As an initial note, it's important to highlight that the project is currently deployed on two servers—one for the pre-production environment and a second for the production environment. The first server functions as a testing environment, allowing the exploration of features before deploying them to the live platform. It also serves as the initial stage for showcases web editing, providing a testing space to learn how to use the platform without risking production integrity.

4.1 External APIs

The Agora of aUPaEU aims to collect information not only regarding the specific outcomes of alliances it collaborates with, but also from external European platforms. This integration is achieved through the access of public APIs, making these resources accessible to other communities. Up to this point, two different platforms have been explored: the EOSC portal, established by the European Union's Horizon 2020 research programme, from where we obtained a list of services and research infrastructures; and eduGAIN, co-founded by the European Union, from where we obtained a list of organisations and institutions together with relevant official data.

4.2 Generic Module

It has been mentioned in previous sections that the Website Odoo application has limitations in displaying lists of elements from a custom Odoo model and creating new entries from such models from the website user interface.

To address this limitation, an add-on has been developed to handle the creation and display of elements from a given model. This development is designed to be generic and adaptable, ensuring compatibility with many similar services planned for this project.

4.2.1 Creation of elements

This functionality has been achieved by extending the existing Form website block. Typically, the form edition displays a selector to choose the action to be performed, with default actions including creating an Opportunity, creating a Task, and sending an Email. In the add-on, two configuration fields have been added, the Custom Form displays a list of all Odoo models, from which an editor user can select and automatically create a new action for creating entries through a form. The fields of the selected model are mapped to possible Form fields, enabling the configuration of additional information about required fields and the addition of descriptions to specific fields.

Examples of this functionality can be found in the example of Research and Innovation proposals in Unite! Agora, and Internships Offers.

Figure 4.1. Form website block customization

4.2.2 List of elements

When it comes to displaying lists of elements from any Odoo model, a new Building Block (also known as Snippet) has been developed. In Odoo, Snippets are XML elements that can be introduced as isolated blocks of code within a website page, allowing for customization of visualisation through configuration parameters (refer to examples in Figure 4.2).

The configuration parameters of the custom List of Elements block offer the following customizations. The most important is the selector of the Odoo model, that determines the model from which to display its entries. Once a model is selected, a list of the model fields is displayed on the editing tab, each with a switch button to determine whether it should be publicly displayed on the website. If the fields apply to possible filters, the user can activate specific filters for a specific field. The types of filters to apply are possible for the following Odoo fields: {many2many, many2one, boolean, selection}, a free text search bar is always configured, which filters for all the text-type fields of the model. The card title is also selectable from all the text fields of the model, typically adopting the “name” or “title” field.

Additionally, there is an option to add a Contact Button to each element, which is an optional feature that creates a custom contact form for a specific element. This allows easy tracking of user engagement in a specific manner. Two selectable fields for defining the Salesperson and the Sales Team associated with such a contact form are also available. Lastly, there are a couple of colour configurations for the card and contact button, as well as desired width and background of the list of elements.

Figure 4.2. Custom Snippet block to display lists of elements on the website

The generated list of elements contains a search bar at the top, allowing users to filter the displayed elements based on a specific topic. This search is a free text search which searches all content of the elements for matching results. When clicking on an element in the list, some information is displayed, and additional details can be accessed on a new page by clicking the "Learn More" button.

Figure 4.3. Selected list element

4.3 Artificial Intelligence Assistant

As we enter a decade where Large Language Models (LLMs) and artificial intelligence (AI) are becoming integral tools across various fields, they are assured to reshape the architecture of existing databases. This project is designed to store extensive databases of infrastructures, research projects, contacts, and interactions within them. It is only logical to explore the potential applications of AI in this platform. This necessity has proven to be a gap yet not resolved by Odoo, as it does not offer integration with LLM systems. In this first stage of the project, we have introduced a new add-on which assesses this situation. Let's first go through the key concepts of machine learning and LLMs.

- Machine learning, a subset of artificial intelligence, involves the creation and exploration of statistical algorithms capable of generalising and executing tasks without explicit instructions.
- Large Language Models (LLMs) are able to achieve general-purpose language understanding and generation. To accomplish specific tasks, the most popular approaches involve applying fine-tuning and prompt engineering.

In the use case of the aUPaEU project, the concept could involve offering users an AI assistant that, through conversation and discussion and with access to the database of records, can guide the user to the desired resource. This could include providing a URL to the specific record, allowing the interested user to contact the resource. Refer to the figure below for a visual representation of the current implementation of this feature.

The architecture used to build the AI assistant has multiple elements. At its core is the connection between a vector database and Odoo. Vector Databases store embedded data in a vectorized form, where vectors define a sentence based on its semantic meaning. A specific external service has been configured to manage this database, providing an API to perform simple CRUD operations and search for similar elements through a semantic search. Given that a typical Odoo environment deploys its database over Postgres, the entries of a specific model such as the Research Infrastructures can be stored to the Vector database through the API service, which will make an embedding of each element using an embedding model to vectorize it.

Figure 4.4. AI assistant

The AI assistance chat process follows the following steps.

1. The end user inputs a query into the Odoo UI
2. The query is transformed into an embedding by the embedding model
3. The vector database uses the query embedding to retrieve a filtered dataset via the RAG process (Retrieval Augmented Generation)
4. The filtered context is fed into a prompt together with the initial query and a previous historic of the conversation, and engineered-prompted
5. The LLM API receives the prompt and generates a text output
6. The LLM output response is displayed to the end user through the Odoo UI
7. This architecture proposes a potential system that integrates machine learning models to better address user requirements, aiming to provide accurate and contextually relevant information to interested users. The approach is still under development and may evolve to meet requirements beyond customer assistance for the aUPaEU project.

Figure 4.5. Architecture of LLM integration assistance

5 Results

In the first place, results can be obtained from the number of active users registered on the platform and the number of contacts stored in the Contact module provided by Odoo. It brings value to analyse the repercussions which may have caused within the two collaborating alliances and the aUPaEU project stakeholders.

Note the difference between Portal and Internal users. Portal users only have access to the websites, they may interact with other users through contact forms but not through the back-office management tool as they do not have access to it. The Internal users are the managers of the platform. Even though different access rights apply to each internal user, the back-office is only available to them.

Analysing the results from the following Table 5.1, detail results are extracted from each Agora (company) at the end of 2023:

- [Unite! Alliance Agora](#) – The Unite! Alliance has been present on the project since the beginning of its development, demonstrating higher engagement, especially with Portal users (136), which primarily involves researchers, teachers and students of the Unite! Community. The Contacts database is also large, comprising over 900 contacts and 42 institutions within the alliance.
- [EPICUR Alliance Agora](#) – EPICUR has recently initiated collaborations with aUPaEU, which explains the smaller network of contacts and users that is still in the process of definition.

- [aUPaEU Project Agora](#) – This Agora is formed by the project's coordination members and active developers of the Agora platform. While the number of users remains relatively stable, it is important that the number of contact institutions is the highest among all companies. As aUPaEU coordinates services for multiple alliances and institutions, it requires information from many institutions over Europe and the world for potential collaborations.
- [Stakeholders Agora](#) - This Agora is the very preliminary open Agora in collaboration with the sister projects: CATALISI, Accelerate Future HEI and aUPaEU

Table 5.1. Data numbers of Users and Contacts

Projects Users and Contacts

Agoras	Users		Stakeholders	
	Internal Users	Portal Users	Individuals	Institutions
Unite!	41	136	906	42
EPICUR	5	5	9	11
aUPaEU	9	19	266	405
Stakeholders	4	6	33	18

5.1 Technical meetings with service users

As mentioned in the first section of this document, all technical implementations developed on this project so far have been the result of a cooperation between different stakeholders.

Setting the focus on the defined list of acceleration services by the WP2 of the aUPaEU project, technical meetings have taken place with users from Unite!, Epicur, and other organisations in which they exposed their service needs to be implemented. The results of those meetings defined a viable solution to fit those needs in the most efficient and unified way possible. As it is crucial for the aUPaEU project to design digital platforms, which can provide acceleration services not only to specific institutions, but flexible enough to adapt to various alliances with different service specifications.

The methodology of creating these developments has therefore been based on a co-creation practice. Offering implementations in a very agile way, receiving feedback from the interested users, and modifying those implementations to adapt best to each user.

The following Table 5.2 presents a record of technical meetings held with various project partners, highlighting the collaboration efforts in developing acceleration services. Each row

in the table represents a specific meeting, detailing the date, the type of acceleration service discussed related to one of the listed on Table 1.1 provided by WP2, the service itself, the associated alliance working group or community, the number of attendees, the participating partners, and additional comments or objectives for the meeting.

Table 5.2. Co-creation meetings with stakeholders

Co-creation meetings

Date	Acc. service	Service	Alliance WG or Cm	Num. of attendees	Attending partners	Comments or objective of meeting
21/04/2023	#5	Research and Innovation Proposals	Iris Pilot	5	UPC	IRIS Pilot (UNITE)
11/05/2023	#2	Research Infrastructures catalogue	WG3	4	UPC, INP Grenoble	WP3- METACAMPUS. Shared infrastructures. Tool update
23/05/2023	#2	Research Infrastructures catalogue	WG3	4	UPC	Talk about the online RI catalogue
13/07/2023	#5	Research and Innovation Proposals	Iris Pilot	5	UPC	Follow-up meeting on the R&I collaboration
23/08/2023	#8	Cm3 virtual showcase	Cm3	5	TUD, Lisboa, UPC	Community 3 Virtual Showcase on Agora Platform
31/08/2023	#8	Cm3 virtual showcase	Cm3	2	TUD, UPC	Showcase configuration specifications
26/09/2023	#2	Research Infrastructures	Epicur and Unite	8	UPC, INP Grenoble, KIT	Joint meeting to discuss Unite! and EPICUR RI catalogues
06/10/2023	#4, #2	AI tool	Unite	5	Wroclaw, UPC	Discussion on Agora and AI tool for Unite! synergies
23/10/2023	#5	Outreach course for students	Unite	5	UPC, TU Graz	Planning a short outreach course for students (Cm9) - last week of November
24/10/2023	#5	Course catalogue	Cm4	3	Aalto, UPC	Next steps with Agora repository and form
27/10/2023	#5	Wellbeing buddies	Cm3	5	TUD, UPC	Wellbeing buddies / Unite! Agora

Date	Acc. service	Service	Alliance WG or Cm	Num. of attendees	Attending partners	Comments or objective of meeting
30/10/2023	#5	Course catalogue	Cm4	2	Aalto, UPC	Offerings Catalogue
03/11/2023	#8	Speech Language and AI showcase	Unite SeedFund	4	UPC, TU Graz	Crossroads of Speech and Language - Teaching and Research Seed Fund Projects
03/11/2023	#5	Course catalogue	Cm4	2	Aalto, UPC	Offerings Catalogue
06/11/2023	#5	Reading Club	Unite SeedFund	3	Aalto, UPC, INP Grenoble	Reading Club space on Agora
08/11/2023	#8	Space tech showcase	Unite SeedFund	6	Aalto, UPC	Agora space for Seed Funding project
9/11/2023	#8	Internships Offers	Cm5.4	5	UPC, INP Grenoble	Internship offers Unite!
15/11/2023	#8	Faculty and Staff showcase	Cm6	4	UPC, INP Grenoble	Showcase Cm.6
17/11/2023	#8	Online Toolkit	Cm4.2	7	Aalto, UPC, KTH, Lisboa	Agora demo for Unite 4.2 online toolkit
23/11/2023	#8	Agora	Coordinators Meeting	11	Aalto, UPC, KTH, Lisboa, INP Grenoble, Wroclaw, TU Graz, TUD	E+ Community Coordinators' Meeting - Unite! Digital Campus
27/11/2023	#8	Online Toolkit	Cm4.2 A	20	Aalto, UPC, KTH, Lisboa, INP Grenoble, Wroclaw, TU Graz, TUD, POLITO	Unite! 4.2 A (joint programmes) handbook check-up
28/11/2023	#5	Welcome Kits	Cm3	10	Aalto, POLITO, KTH, Lisboa, Wroclaw	Unite! Welcome Kits at Agora
29/11/2023				9	UPC, Wroclaw	Workshop on Unite! Agora AI and Future Opportunities
30/11/2023	#8	AgriTech	X AgriTech	4	UPC, IRTA	Agora Xarxa X_AgriTech

Date	Acc. service	Service	Alliance WG or Cm	Num. of attendees	Attending partners	Comments or objective of meeting
1/12/2023	#5	Reading Club	Unite SeedFund	5	Aalto, UPC, INP Grenoble	Unite! Reading Club
12/12/2023	#5	Course catalogue	Cm4	2	Aalto, UPC	Configuration of Agora Form
19/12/2023	#8	Faculty and Staff showcase	Cm6	3	UPC, INP Grenoble	Faculty and Staff showcase
20/12/2023	#8	Virtual Inclusion Office	Cm3	5	UPC, Lisboa	Unite! Agora and Unite! Cm3 Virtual Inclusion Office WG

For terminology purposes, In the column **Alliance WG or Cm**, WG means the working group of Unite! H2020 project, Cm means de community of the E+ Unite! project, Unite SeedFund are projects that have been accepted in the Unite! SeedFund initiative, and those without specific groups are traversal to Unite or EPICUR alliances.

6 References

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